

SI Table S1: Details of analysis of steroids by LC-MS/MS. A volume of 2 μ L was injected into an Agilent 1260 infinity II LC system, consisting of a binary pump G7112B, an autosampler G7167A and a column thermostat G7116A (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) without preconcentration or filtering. Chromatographic separation was carried out on a ZORBAX Eclipse XDB-C18 column (50 \times 4.6 mm, 1.8 μ m) from Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA). A binary solvent system was used as mobile phase consisting of A) 0.05% formic acid in water and B) acetonitrile with a constant flow rate of 1.1 mL/min at 20 $^{\circ}$ C column temperature. The following gradient was applied: 0.00-0.50 min, 60% A; 0.50-5.00 min, 60-10% A; 5.00-5.05 min, 10-0% A; 5.05-6.50 min, 0% A; 6.50-6.55 min, 0-60% A; 6.55-9.00 min, 60% A. The column outlet was connected to a QTRAP 6500+ triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (AB Sciex LLC, Framingham, MA, USA). The Turbo Spray IonDrive ion source was running in positive ionization mode with 5500 V ion spray voltage and 650 $^{\circ}$ C turbo gas temperature. The curtain gas was set to 40 psi; the collision gas to 'medium' and both ion source gases 1 & 2 were set to 70 psi. Scheduled multiple reaction monitoring (scheduled MRM) was used to monitor analyte parent ion \rightarrow product ion fragmentations as described in table 1. Q1 and Q3 quadrupoles were maintained at unit resolution. Analyst 1.6 software (Applied Biosystems) was used for data acquisition and processing. Nona-deuterated progesterone (PO- d_9) was used as internal standard (IS) for quantification. The response factors (analyte \times standard $^{-1}$) of individual steroids relative to the internal standard have been experimentally determined. The table shows mass to charge ratio (m/z), retention time (RT), collision energy (CE) and the response factor to the used internal standard (f).

Compound	Usage:	m/z :	RT [min]	CE [V]	f
PR	Quantifier	299 \rightarrow 281	4.29	15	0.49
	Qualifier	317 \rightarrow 299		13	
PO	Quantifier	315 \rightarrow 97	4.43	25	1.23
	Qualifier	315 \rightarrow 109		30	
DHP	Quantifier	317 \rightarrow 299	5.31	17	0.23
	Qualifier	317 \rightarrow 281		19	
17 α -OHPR-	Quantifier	315 \rightarrow 297	2.80	13	0.11
	Qualifier	333 \rightarrow 297		13	
DHEA	Quantifier	289 \rightarrow 271	3.01	9	0.08
	Qualifier	289 \rightarrow 253		15	
17 α -OHPO	Quantifier	331 \rightarrow 97	3.15	27	0.57
	Qualifier	331 \rightarrow 109		30	
AD	Quantifier	287 \rightarrow 211	3.07	27	0.09
	Qualifier	287 \rightarrow 173		29	
TO	Quantifier	289 \rightarrow 97	2.58	25	1.34
	Qualifier	289 \rightarrow 109		30	
DHT	Quantifier	291 \rightarrow 255	3.45	21	0.84
	Qualifier	291 \rightarrow 273		19	
PO- D_9	Quantifier	324 \rightarrow 100	4.43	29	-